

Supplementary Information for: Deciphering Global Patterns of Marine Microbial Community Assembly and Network Stability

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1 Supplementary Information

2 Supplementary Files

- 3 • Supplementary File 1: Metadata of the samples
- 4 • Supplementary File 2: Denoising Parameters
- 5 • Supplementary File 3: Denoising Statistics

6 Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. Data used in this study. The number of samples taken from each study and the respective accession IDs are shown.

Project	Number of Samples	Relevant Project IDs
Earth Microbiome Project	1405	QIITA IDs 10178, 678, 713, 723, 905, 1039, 1235, 1240
Tara Oceans Project	169	PRJEB36282, PRJEB36283
Malaspina Expedition	320	PRJEB25224, PRJEB45011, PRJEB27154
Global Ocean Sampling	47	PRJEB40762
Bio-GO-SHIP	465	PRJNA656268
Australian Microbiome Project	2369	PRJNA1122929

Supplementary Table 2: Multivariate Analysis of Microbial Beta Diversity Using PERMANOVA The results show the R^2 , which indicates the variation captured by each covariate, and the p -value indicates the significance of the results.

Factors	R^2 value	p -value
Latitude Zones	0.046	0.001
Oceans	0.027	0.001
Sample Origin	0.067	0.001
Project	0.037	0.001

Supplementary Table 3: Canonical Correspondence Analysis of Marine Microbial Community Structure and Environmental Drivers The table shows the correlation of environmental variables with the first two canonical axes (CCA1 and CCA2). It includes the coefficient of determination (R^2), indicating the strength of the relationship, and the statistical significance (p -value), indicating whether the observed correlation is significant.

Variable	CCA1	CCA2	R^2	p -value
Latitude Zone	-0.220	-0.975	0.648	0.05
Oceans	-0.850	-0.526	0.043	0.05
Sample Origin	0.997	-0.080	0.733	0.05

Supplementary Table 4A: ANOVA-Based Comparison of Microbial Alpha Diversity Across Latitude Zones, Oceans, and Sample Origins. Results of ANOVA on the Shannon Diversity Index. Effect sizes are reported as R^2 (proportion of variance explained), calculated from the sum of squares.

Factor	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F-value	Pr (>F)	R^2
Latitude Zones	2	232.4	116.22	248.13	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	0.105
Oceans	3	16.9	5.63	12.02	7.83×10^{-8}	0.008
Sample Origin	3	143.0	47.65	101.74	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	0.065

Supplementary Table 4B: ANOVA-Based Comparison of Microbial Alpha Diversity Across Latitude Zones, Oceans, and Sample Origins. Results of ANOVA on the Chao1 richness index. Effect sizes are reported as R^2 (proportion of variance explained), calculated from the sum of squares.

Factor	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F-value	Pr (>F)	R^2
Latitude Zones	2	2447876	1223938	252.72	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	0.110
Oceans	3	220264	73421	15.16	8.3×10^{-10}	0.010
Sample Origin	3	840737	280246	57.87	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	0.038

Supplementary Table 5: Kruskal-Wallis test on the differentially abundant phyla in each latitude zone The table shows phyla whose abundance distributions differ significantly between zones. The zone in which they are differentially abundant and the associated p -values are indicated.

Phyla	p -value	Latitude Zone
<i>Campylobacterota</i>	3.78×10^{-191}	Polar
<i>Verrucomicrobiota</i>	6.45×10^{-181}	Temperate
<i>Marinisomatota</i>	9.62×10^{-225}	Tropical

Supplementary Table 6: Topological Roles of Genera in Latitude-Specific Co-occurrence Networks Percentage of microbial genera classified as Peripherals, Connectors, and Module Hubs within the Polar, Temperate, and Tropical co-occurrence networks

Group	Connectors	Module Hubs	Peripherals
Polar	8.11%	1.10%	90.81%
Temperate	16.55%	1.63%	81.81%
Tropical	6.76%	2.15%	91.07%

Supplementary Table 7: Null model analysis on the PERMDISP results This table illustrates the comparison between observed dispersion patterns and those expected under random assembly processes, helping to infer the ecological mechanisms driving community variability.

Group	Dissimilarity (Observed)	Dissimilarity (Null)	F-value	<i>p</i> -value
Polar	0.354	0.498	0.86	< 0.001
Temperate	0.545	0.498	0.89	< 0.001
Tropical	0.434	0.498	1.28	< 0.001

7 Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1: Geographic Distribution of the samples The samples utilised in the study are geographically mapped and colour-coded based on the dataset from which it is obtained

Supplementary Figure 2: Scree plot depicting variation caused by each of the principal components .

Supplementary Figure 3A: The degree distribution of the latitude-specific co-occurrence networks Degree Distribution of polar microbial co-occurrence networks.

Supplementary Figure 3B: The degree distribution of the latitude-specific co-occurrence networks Degree Distribution of temperate microbial co-occurrence networks.

Supplementary Figure 3C: The degree distribution of the latitude-specific co-occurrence networks Degree Distribution of tropical microbial co-occurrence networks.

Supplementary Figure 4: Natural Connectivity of the networks as nodes of the highest degree are removed sequentially The variations in the natural connectivity after sequentially removing genera of the highest degree in polar, tropical and temperate networks (colour-coded).

Supplementary Figure 5: Number of inter- and intra-phyla interactions of the generalists and the specialists.

Supplementary Figure 6A: The degree distribution of the sample-origin-specific co-occurrence networks Degree Distribution of coral microbial co-occurrence networks.

Supplementary Figure 6B: The degree distribution of the sample-origin-specific co-occurrence networks Degree Distribution of marine microbial co-occurrence networks.

Supplementary Figure 6C: The degree distribution of the sample-origin-specific co-occurrence networks Degree Distribution of marine sediment microbial co-occurrence networks.

Supplementary Figure 6D: The degree distribution of the sample-origin-specific co-occurrence networks Degree Distribution of sponge microbial co-occurrence networks.